

CLINICAL AND MEDICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF THE TREATMENT OF THE HUMAN ORGANISM WITH LEECH

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Abstract.

Hirudotherapy "treatment with leeches" is a method of treatment that has reached us over the centuries. Medicinal leeches are the only representatives of the fauna [animal world], which are included in pharmacology and equated to medicinal substances. The history of hirudotherapy covers more than two thousand years. Ancient Greece, in India, Egypt, China, treatment with leeches was popular. Images of leeches began to appear on the walls of the tombs of the Egyptian pharaohs.

Key words.

history of hirudotherapy, healing effect of leeches on the human body, instructions, treatment with leeches, benefits and harms, how the treatment is carried out.

Main part: Hirudotherapy [Latin hirudo-"leech" therapy is Greek for "healing". This physiotherapeutic treatment is considered to be an alternative medicine. Such leeches are the only species belonging to the small class of worms, the others do not have such a healing effect. The history of gyrudotherapy spans more than two thousand years. It gained wide popularity at the beginning of the century. Almost all diseases were treated with this method. During this period, leeches are grown on an industrial scale and begin to be exported between countries. All pharmacies will start selling leeches. If we look at history, archeologists found a lot of information about leeches in the materials found in the remains of the old library during the excavations. It is recorded in the manuscripts that doctors have obtained excellent results as a result of treatment with leeches. .Invented in the Middle Ages,

hirudotherapy was found to help with obesity, at that time overweight was one of the most important problems in many countries. As a result of treatment with leeches, excellent results have been achieved. People have lost 10-12 kg of weight and noted that their health has improved. Treatment with leeches was also popular in Egypt, many diseases were cured by leeches. According to legend, Queen Cleopatra, who suffered from infertility, was able to conceive Julius Caesar thanks to the magical influence of leeches. After that, images of leeches began to appear on the walls of the tombs of Egyptian pharaohs. Leeches belong to the class of ringworms, there are about 400 species of them, and they are distributed in freshwater basins and seas. The back and belly sides of the body are flattened, sometimes cylindrical in shape. Two types of leeches are used in medicine. When medical leeches are called a cure for a thousand diseases, they do not exaggerate their properties, but they reduce the properties of these wonderful magical creatures. Medical leeches have 5 pairs of eyes on their heads, and 3 jaws with chitinous teeth in their mouths. With their help, the leech bites the skin at a depth of 1.5-2 mm and sucks blood in the amount of 5-15 ml. Leeches are actually very sensitive and cannot tolerate foreign smells. If the skin smells of soap, gel, shampoo, and perfume products, leeches may stick to the skin and have difficulty sucking blood. Therefore, before applying the leeches to the skin, washing off the odors and odorous products, baby soap or laundry soap will help to remove the odors from the skin and kill bacteria. There are specific rules for attaching medical leeches to the human body. When determining the place where the leech is placed, attention is paid to the type of disease, the level of inflammation, and the condition of the patient. The treatment lasts from 25-30 minutes to an hour, depending on the type of disease. it is released and gets into the blood. Hirudin secreted by leech contains about 100 biologically active substances that have a positive effect on the normal functioning of the body. These natural substances include hirudin, hyaluronidase, destabilase, eglins, antibiotics and anesthetics. Destabilase enzyme is a substance that causes blood clots to break up and be absorbed. Hyaluronidase actively participates in the absorption of scar diseases. It is considered an enzyme that reduces the wounding and inflammation of the skin tissues. In the case of premature removal of leeches, it is impossible to pluck or cut off leeches. Otherwise, the leech's head will stick and suck blood again, causing the patient's condition to worsen. According to medical measures, leeches are removed from the skin using alcohol or iodine solution. When the leech is full of blood, it falls off. Once used leeches are killed with chloramine solution and buried. After 1-24 hours,

the leeches will bleed from the bite mark. 4-10 leeches are placed in one treatment session. With the help of leeches, it has been used against many diseases: including

*In hypertensive diseases: blood pressure increase, various thrombophlebitis.

*Urology: prostatitis, prostate adenoma, urinary tract stones.

*In skin diseases: psoriasis, neurodermatitis, eczema, acne breakouts.

*In cardiology: Atherosclerosis, cardiosclerosis.

* In gynecology, it is recommended to apply leech in diseases such as menstrual disorders, uterine fibroids, inflammation of the ovaries.

Summary: "Cases where it is not possible to use". It cannot be used in case of suffering from blood clotting system problems, oncological diseases, hemophilia, pregnant women, long-term and heavy bleeding, depression, anxiety, chronic fatigue. The damage that leeches can cause depends on their diet and specific structure, so the following problems are likely.

1. Active substances cause high exposure of the skin, i.e. redness and similar conditions.

2. Due to blood-thinning enzymes in leech juice, bleeding occurs for a while at the wound site.

3. In the gastrointestinal tract of the leech, there is a bacterium that protects the leech from infection when sucking "diseased" blood. These bacteria can harm people and mucous membranes can cause diseases!

REFERENCES:

(1) "Amur State Medical Academy". O.M. Gongarova, E. V. Lobanova. in 2016.

(2) Girudoterapiya pri boleznyakh system' krovoobrashcheniya V. A. Jernov. J. A. Kolateva. in 2015